

Adverse health effects resulting from the consumption of snake mackerel

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For a number of years, products labelled “smoked snake mackerel” or “smoked oilfish” have been among the fish products available on the German market. These include fish of different species which is very fatty and primarily marketed as smoked foods. Reports from Germany and other countries have indicated that following the consumption of larger amounts of such fish products, sensitive individuals may experience gastrointestinal ailments as a result of these. These ailments were temporary and occurred shortly after consumption. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has received reports of 26 cases of German consumers with such health ailments since 2005. These are attributed to the large amount of wax ester contained in the fat or oil of these fishes. The BfR warns of the risks of possible health ailments after the consumption of such fish products.

The full version of the BfR Information in German is available on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/208/gesundheitsbeeintraechtigungen_durch_den_verzehr_von_buttermakrelen.pdf